

Automated Real-Time Localized Sea State Estimation During Navigation Based on the Beaufort Scale

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Abstract—This work presents an automated, real-time approach for localized sea state estimation using a single camera mounted on a ship's bridge. A labeled dataset of sea surface images, collected during regular operation of an overseas liner, is built and used to train deep neural networks to estimate sea state on the Beaufort scale from 1 to 8. To improve robustness and better capture operational variability, a substantially enlarged test set is constructed relative to previous work, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation under diverse navigation and environmental conditions. Additionally, to mitigate the scarcity of rarely occurring sea states in real-world operation, a synthetic training dataset is generated that simulates a wide range of sea and weather conditions while preserving key physical relationships to increase variability in illumination and wave appearance without degrading realism. We evaluated state-of-the-art convolutional and transformer-based architectures, including Resnet-101d, DeiT III, Swin transformer, XcIT and CoAtNet. The impact of different synthetic-to-real training data ratios in both RGB and grayscale domains is systematically examined, yielding a 6% improvement in test accuracy and mean F1 score and a reduction of the maximum error from 7 to 3 Beaufort. Finally, a temporal voting framework that aggregates predictions over several consecutive frames further reduces the maximum error to 2 Beaufort and achieves 96% intra-1-class accuracy and an F1 score of 62%, substantially outperforming a baseline trained only on real data without temporal voting.

Impact Statement — The maritime industry is increasingly adopting artificial intelligence to enhance operational efficiency, improve navigational safety and achieve sustainability goals. Ensuring navigational safety, as well as the environmental and economic efficiency of maritime operations, requires an accurate assessment of sea state. Traditionally, sea state is visually assessed using the Beaufort scale, which relates wind speed to sea surface state and classifies it into 13 classes (0-12). Since this method relies on visual observation, it is subjective and prone to human error, so automating sea state assessment using computer vision methods can provide an effective monitoring alternative. The models proposed in this paper achieved intra-1-class accuracy of 96% on a varied test set, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach for robust sea state estimation.

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Index Terms—computer vision, deep neural networks, sea state recognition, synthetic dataset

I. INTRODUCTION

THE maritime industry is increasingly adopting artificial intelligence and machine learning to enhance operational safety, improve efficiency and achieve sustainability goals. One key application is the integration of machine learning into automation and autonomous shipboard decision support systems which aim to improve safety by reducing human error [1]. Separately, these technologies contribute to the International Maritime Organization's (IMO) environmental objectives, such as lowering greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and improving ship energy efficiency [2], [3].

To ensure navigational safety as well as the environmental and economic efficiency of maritime operations, accurate assessment of sea state is vital [4]. When encountering heavy seas, ships can employ maneuvers like altering course or reducing speed to minimize risks and lower energy consumption [5]. The use of machine learning for route optimization based on real-time meteorological and oceanographic data has been shown to reduce fuel consumption and GHG emissions significantly [6], [7], [8]. However, the widespread adoption of machine learning in maritime automation and autonomous navigation depends on the reliability and accuracy of these systems, which are significantly influenced by the quality of input data [9]. As sensor technology advances, integrating localized environmental and sea state information is expected to positively impact model accuracy and predictive capabilities [10].

Sea state is commonly assessed using the Beaufort scale, which correlates wind speed with sea surface state and classifies them into 13 classes (0-12). Since visual assessments are inherently subjective and prone to human error, automating sea

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state evaluation using computer vision methods can provide more objective and reliable alternative for continuous monitoring.

Recent developments in computer vision have highlighted its potential for automated sea state estimation. However, the highly dynamic and variable nature of the marine environment continues to present substantial challenges. Sea surface conditions are shaped by wind, currents, tides, seabed topography, and variations in temperature and salinity, all of which complicate accurate observation and modeling [11]. In addition, visual appearance is strongly affected by sea color, which changes with location and depth: open ocean waters darken with depth due to light absorption, while coastal and shallow areas often display green or brown hues influenced by phytoplankton and sediments. Environmental factors such as sunlight, surface reflections, and limited visibility under cloudy, rainy, or foggy conditions further impact image quality.

These complexities make robust sea state classification difficult and require computer vision systems trained on diverse datasets that span a wide range of sea states, geographic regions, depths, seabed characteristics, time of day, and weather conditions. Camera dynamics add another layer of difficulty, as moving platforms, particularly when mounted on a moving ship with six degrees of freedom, introduce variability in perspective and field of view that affects model performance. Addressing these challenges requires the development of adaptable computer vision systems capable of delivering reliable sea state assessments across heterogeneous operational and environmental contexts, with the broader aim of supporting autonomous navigation and enhancing maritime safety.

Expanding upon prior research [12], this work aims to improve model robustness and generalization for automated sea state assessment through the integration of synthetic data and advanced network architectures.

Recognizing that the commonly used Beaufort scale discretizes sea states into 13 levels, while the true wave heights and wind speeds form a continuous spectrum, we employ both classification and regression frameworks for evaluation. Model performance for discrete sea state classification is measured using precision, recall, and F1 scores, while for continuous prediction, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and maximum error are utilized. This dual assessment approach reflects the practical reality that misclassification severity varies with the distance between predicted and actual states—misclassifying sea state 3 as 4 is less consequential than as 7. Through this methodology, our study provides a comprehensive and practical evaluation framework, advancing the accuracy and reliability of sea state estimation models in complex operational environments.

The contributions of this paper can be summarized as:

- 1) A hybrid UNIRI-SeaState dataset consisting of sea state images ranging from 1 to 8 Bft and synthetically generated images together with a synthetic data generation procedure that ensures a faithful simulation in order to increase variability and overcome environmental constraints without compromising realism.
- 2) A comprehensive quantitative analysis and similarity

comparison of real-world data captured across diverse navigation operations that reflect domain shifts and the gap between real and synthetic data according to the FID/FAISS metric.

- 3) A temporal framework of fine-tuned Vision Transformers that aggregates predictions from sequential video frames, thereby mitigating transient classification errors and stabilizing sea state estimation, resulting in a 7% improvement in accuracy over single-frame models. The final model achieves a within-1-class accuracy of 96% and a mean average error (MAE) below 0.56 on the UNIRI-SeaState multi-vessel test set.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the related work, Section 3 covers the dataset background including synthetic data generation, Section 4 reviews the model architectures used, Section 5 covers the experimental setup and the evaluation methods employed. Section 6 discusses the experimental results and their implications for practical applications. Finally, Section 7 concludes with recommendations for future research directions in robust sea state recognition.

II. RELATED WORK

Machine learning techniques have been widely applied in the estimation of sea states, providing a robust alternative to traditional physical and numerical models. In one of the earlier studies, neural networks were employed to provide short-term ocean wave forecasting, with lead times ranging from 3 to 24 hours. The method compared different training algorithms and demonstrated the utility of neural networks for generating accurate and timely forecasts, essential for maritime operations [13].

A subsequent study applied a multilayer perceptron (MLP) model to predict significant wave heights, utilizing optimized weighting coefficients derived through genetic algorithms. The geno-MLP approach showed better predictive capabilities compared to traditional back-propagation algorithms, illustrating the effectiveness of machine learning techniques in wave prediction [14]. More recently, a real-time prediction model for significant wave heights was developed, utilizing both artificial neural networks (ANN) and support vector machines (SVM). This model was designed to predict wave heights over short-term intervals, with the incorporation of wind data significantly improving the accuracy of predictions [15]. In the most recent contribution, a machine learning-based approach for sea state estimation was developed using in-situ sensor data from an advancing container vessel. The study compared time and frequency domain models, with multiple deep neural networks (DNNs) being trained. An Inception Architecture tailored for sequential data yielded the best performance, and the frequency domain model was found to be superior in both accuracy and computational efficiency [16]. Collectively, these studies underscore the evolving role of machine learning techniques in advancing sea state estimation, with applications ranging from short-term wave forecasting to real-time sea state assessments for autonomous shipping and

navigation.

One of the most promising technological advancements in the domain of environmental and situational awareness is computer vision. Computer vision systems enable real-time awareness, allowing intelligent transportation systems to detect, classify, and respond to their surroundings [17], [18], [19]. The integration of computer vision based sea state recognition facilitates autonomous vessels in making data-driven decisions that enhance navigational safety, optimize fuel consumption, and mitigate risks associated with adverse maritime conditions [12]. Moreover, real-time sea state recognition enables the generation of precise and timely weather models, which are invaluable for route planning, risk management, and the overall sustainability of marine operations [20].

Recent advancements, such as those proposed in [21], demonstrate the importance of integrating domain-specific knowledge, such as ship characteristics and sailing speed, into computer vision models to improve recognition and prediction accuracy in complex marine environments. This integration is especially valuable for overcoming challenges posed by environmental variability, such as changing light conditions, wave patterns, and the presence of multiple ships, ensuring more robust decision-making in autonomous systems. The difficulty of obtaining or labeling sufficient real training data in different weather conditions for robust training of models in applications in intelligent transport systems has prompted researchers to explore different approaches such as semi-supervised [22] and unsupervised domain adaptation [23], and augmentation of real data with synthetic data [24].

Recent years have witnessed the adoption of various deep neural network approaches for automated sea state assessment. For instance, in [25] a ResNet-152 architecture was developed to classify 10 sea state categories from video footage captured by ship-mounted cameras, achieving a validation accuracy of 89.3%, although details regarding test accuracy and standard scale alignment were not provided. Similarly, deep learning methods applied to Beaufort scale states 1–4 achieved a test accuracy of 97.8% [26], while random forest algorithms obtained 90.5% accuracy for sea state recognition using in-service vessel data [16]. The Leucotea project introduces an advanced system that integrates convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and optical flow analysis for coastal wave monitoring, leveraging both fixed and mobile camera footage to evaluate wave dynamics and tide phases [27].

Despite the progress made, there was no model adapted for use on an ocean-going ship and capable of recognizing sea states in its entire operational spectrum, which is usually up to sea state 6. Sea states 7 and 8 are actively avoided during navigation for safety reasons, due to increased fuel consumption and higher CO₂ emissions, and difficult maritime operations, so they can rarely be recorded. To address these limitations, we developed the customized UNIRI-SeaState dataset [12], comprising sea surface images captured from the bridge of an ocean-going vessel. The dataset includes sea states ranging from 1 to 8 Bft and was used to optimize several state-of-the-art models for real-time sea state classification. The ResNet model gave the best results with an average F1 of 97%,

followed by the ViT model (95.6%), while lighter architectures such as NASNet and MobileNet achieved F1 results of 90% and 85%, respectively [12].

These results demonstrate that both high-complexity models and lightweight models offer practical, flexible solutions for real-time marine monitoring, extending conventional marine observation systems.

III. CREATION OF A CUSTOM SEA STATE DATASET

A. Dataset description

For training and testing the models for sea state estimation, an image dataset annotated with the ground truth sea states is required. Building upon our previous work, in this study we use a variant of the UNIRI-SeaState dataset, which was extensively documented in [12] for training the models. The UNIRI-SeaState dataset consists of sea state images captured from an 89,432 DWT liquefied natural gas transport vessel with the overall length of 293 meters, across 11 distinct geographic locations in Atlantic and Indian Ocean, covering Beaufort scale states 1 through 8. The camera was mounted on the port bridge wing of the vessel at a height ranging from 38-40 m above the sea level. Given that this is a large ship, relatively stable in Bft 1- 6 conditions, we could treat the camera as fixed. Sea states corresponding to 0 Bft and above 8 Bft were not captured during the recording of the dataset, due to the sea state 0 or “calm” being relatively rare in the operating environment of the oceangoing vessel, and conditions above 8 Bft are actively avoided for operational safety and energy efficiency on the ship. In vessel operation, sea states approaching 8 Bft are less frequently encountered, and thus represented with fewer videos and lesser variety of appearance in the dataset. Sea states above 8 were not encountered and recorded at all, so we exclude them from the study.

While we maintain a similar fundamental structure as our previous dataset, we have slightly modified the image cropping strategy to better capture wave patterns. As before, we extract 331×331-pixel segments from the source 4096×2160 frames, but instead of bottom-left corner sampling we use an origin point of (466, 369), as shown in Fig. 1. This modification was made based on our analysis that this region provides more consistent wave pattern visibility while minimizing the presence of ship wake in the images.

Fig. 1. Full video frame and crop area (yellow box).

TABLE I. CLASS DISTRIBUTION IN THE REAL IMAGE DATASETS

UNIRI-SeaState datasets of real images		Sea state (Bft)								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Total
Training set	unique videos	42	13	18	15	17	12	2	2	121
	R150 frames	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	1,200
	R750 frames	750	750	750	750	750	750	750	750	6,000
Test set	unique videos	4	12	16	19	20	10	7	2	90
	Frames	240	450	570	660	660	420	210	210	3,420

To form a balanced dataset, frames were extracted at regular intervals from the videos so that the resulting number of frames for each class is approximately the same. We have prepared two versions of the training set, one with 750 images per class (named UNIRI-SeaState-R750, labeled R750), and one with 150 images per class (named UNIRI-SeaState-R150, labeled R150). The final datasets have the balanced distribution of exactly 750 or 150 images per class, however extracted from varying number of initial videos, according to availability (Table I).

In this study, we employ a new, substantially expanded, and more challenging test set collected one year later from a different, smaller 174 m gas carrier operating on an alternative route, ensuring an unbiased assessment of performance in novel environments. Test videos were recorded at multiple locations across the Atlantic and Indian Oceans with diverse geographic areas captured during navigation and anchoring, under different weather conditions, to rigorously assess the robustness of the model. For each recorded video, the sea state was visually estimated on the Beaufort scale by human experts, as is typical in ship operations. As for the training set, we extract 331×331-pixel segments from the video frames, but here we extract a multiple of 30 frames from each video.

As the data was recorded during typical voyages, the distribution of the collected sea state videos in the test set reflects the common encountered conditions, with very calm and severe conditions being rare, as in the training set. An overview of sea state class distribution in the train and test sets per video and per frame is shown in Table I.

An example image for each represented sea state is shown in Fig. 2. Appearance of the same sea state may vary significantly due to the shape and direction of the waves themselves, as well as weather conditions, angle of the Sun, etc., as is shown in Fig. 3, representing different examples of 5 Bft sea state images in the dataset.

Fig. 2. Examples of extracted sea state images. Top row: states from 1 to 4 Bft. Bottom row: states from 5 to 8 Bft.

Fig. 3. Examples of variability of appearance within the same class (5Bft).

B. Synthetic Data

Recording sea states in real operational scenarios is challenging due to the vast range of appearances influenced by factors like weather, time of day, and ship orientation. This is particularly true for higher Beaufort scale (Bft) conditions, which are often avoided during navigation. To address this limitation and expand the existing UNIRI-SeaState dataset, we

opted to create a synthetic dataset (synthset). The synthset generation method allowed us to vary parameters such as time of day and the relative angles between waves and the camera, thereby achieving a diverse range of appearances for each class. Additionally, this approach enabled us to easily balance classes by generating a desired number of images for each category.

When selecting a method to generate our synthetic dataset, we evaluated game engines and digital content creation (DCC) tools based on established recommendations [28]. Although game engines offer real-time image generation, preliminary experiments (Fig. 4) revealed that their technical limitations and simplifications result in insufficient visual similarity and photorealism, failing to bridge the gap between real and generated images. Specifically, game engines model the water surface by displacing mesh geometry and applying foam textures. In contrast, DCC methods provide precise control over key factors such as wave shape influenced by local wind, swell or distance from the shore, changes in sea color, and foam formation and appearance under various atmospheric conditions. This level of control ensures a more realistic representation of the sea, leading us to choose DCC despite its longer image generation time.

Fig. 4. Left to right: real image; image synthesized using Realistic Ocean Simulator [29] plugin for Unreal Engine; image synthesized using our SeaStateSynth method.

1) Synthset Generation

To generate synthetic datasets that accurately represent various sea states under different atmospheric conditions, we developed the SeaStateSynth method using SideFX Houdini 20.0.547 as a digital content creation tool. This approach involves several critical steps proposed in a pipeline (Fig. 5) to

ensure realistic and adaptive simulations of diverse marine synthsets.

Due to computational demands, we decided to generate the 331 px images matching the crop size in the real dataset instead of generating the whole scene, by varying the focal length, pitch, and yaw of the virtual camera. This approach allowed us to efficiently generate and render only the waves visible within the predefined crop.

Because we don't have examples of sea state images above 8 Bft in either our training or test datasets, we exclude them from the synthset as well, since we don't have reliable reference for setting the synthesis parameters and cannot evaluate their usefulness for training the sea state classification models or their similarity to real data.

The SeaStateSynth pipeline begins with an optical calibration of the virtual camera using real images as references. During optical calibration, the 2D cropped area is converted into a corresponding 3D surface. The wave generator then allows the adjustment of the appearance of the waves on the specified surface for each Beaufort class, resulting in a wave spectrum that is used for foam simulation and, together with the physical sky settings (determined in the lighting phase), for rendering. The correctness of the generated waves is subjectively assessed by visually comparing them with reference images. These assessments are used to further tune the wave generator. Once satisfactory results are achieved, the complete synthset is rendered. The key elements of the method are described in more detail below:

Optical calibration: The process begins with the optical calibration of the virtual camera, ensuring that its properties, such as focal length, height, pitch, yaw, and resolution, match those of a real camera. In our case, camera location and rotations are known in advance since the camera rig is fixed on the ship. We vary cameras and image resolutions. Resolution can be read from the image directly, as opposed to focal length, which is frequently missing from image metadata or is incorrect. Therefore, the primary concern for optical calibration is the determination of the focal length.

Fig. 5. SeaStateSynth method overview

Fig. 6. **Left:** Blueprints of the ship, used to decide where measuring (purple) lines will be drawn over the reference photo (images on the right) and to measure distance from the (cyan) line, representing camera Z position, to each measuring line (purple), for replicating these lines in 3D. **Top-right:** uncalibrated virtual camera with mismatched purple and cyan (3D) lines. **Bottom-right:** calibrated virtual camera (cyan and purple measurement lines overlap within 1 px) showing distances (yellow numbers) from the camera to each corner point and the center of the crop (red bounding box on the left).

It is carried out manually in 3 steps. In the first step, using the blueprints of the ship, at least 3 maximally spaced (by the length of the ship) measurement lines are drawn over a reference photo taken from the centerline of the ship (in order to eliminate the influence of yaw, which, according to the results of our experiments, can introduce a significant error of 1 mm when determining the focal length). In the second step, using the known height of the camera (mounted on the ship), its position is replicated in the 3D scene, the pitch is adjusted (according to the horizon line), and the measurement lines are reconstructed in 3D space. Finally, in the third step, by changing the focal length of the virtual camera, we search for the one in which all measurement lines overlap within the allowed threshold (1 px), as shown in Fig. 6.

After matching the focal length of virtual and real cameras, the raycasting method [30] is used to find the position of the crop's corner points in 3D space and measure the distances between them along with the surface area. This step is essential for accurately synthesizing waves and other 3D sea features within the crop. By replicating the camera's position in the 3D scene to the known height of the camera mounted on the ship and adjusting its pitch according to the horizon line, we ensure that the cropped area is at a same distance from both real and virtual cameras.

This calibration is crucial for maintaining consistency in wave size and appearance.

Waves generator: We utilize the EncinoWaves implementation [31], based on the TMA (Texel-Marsen-Arlose) spectrum [32], to simulate waves for each Beaufort class (Fig. 7). This method allows for near real-time wave shaping, which is vital for efficiently generating diverse sea states. The TMA spectrum is particularly useful for simulating waves in shallow waters, where wave height is limited by depth. In our experiment the distance was set to 3-300 km from the coast, and a sea depth was fixed to 3000 m. By fine-tuning the waves generator for each Beaufort class in the range 1-8 Bft, we achieve a realistic spectrum of waves that align with real-world appearance.

Aiming for maximum wind speed and maximum wave height for each Beaufort, we iteratively fine-tuned the waves generator for 8 classes (Beauforts 1-8) and 3 different distances from the shore (3, 30, and 300 km) using a fixed sea depth (3000 m), until we reached the parameter values shown in Table II. With the given parameters, we created 180 wave variants for each of the 8 Beauforts at each of the 3 distances from the shore (4,320 waves in total), rotating the waves by 2° to cover the full wave direction range ($0-360^\circ$).

Foam simulation: Due to the different nature of foam, foam was generated using particle simulation. It took 5 generations to control the appearance and development of the foam over time to visually resemble real foam.

Reference object simulation: To enhance visual perception and facilitate subjective evaluation of wave size, we add reference objects such as swimmers, boats, or ships to the 3D scene. These objects simulate motion in accordance with wave movement, helping us adjust wave generator parameters until the relationship between waves and reference objects appears realistic.

TABLE II. FINE-TUNED PARAMETERS' VALUES (MAXIMUM WIND SPEED PER BEAUFORT NUMBER, AMPLITUDE SCALE, AND MINIMUM CUSP PER GIVEN DISTANCE) USED FOR GENERATING BFT 1-8 SPECTRA OF WAVES WITH FOAM AND RESULTING MAXIMUM WAVE HEIGHTS THAT CORRESPOND TO THE BEAUFORT SCALE.

Bft #	Max wind speed	Amplitude scale			Min cusp			Resulting max wave height (m)
		3 km	30	300	3 km	30	300	
1	1.50	4.00	1.00	0.40	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.30
2	3.30	3.50	1.00	0.40	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.60
3	5.40	4.00	1.40	0.55	0.25	0.25	0.25	1.20
4	7.90	4.50	1.40	0.80	0.25	0.25	0.25	2.00
5	10.70	4.50	1.70	0.95	0.25	0.25	0.25	3.00
6	13.80	4.70	1.90	1.00	0.20	0.25	0.20	4.00
7	17.10	6.10	2.10	1.00	0.15	0.25	0.15	5.50
8	20.70	5.80	2.50	1.10	0.10	0.25	0.10	7.50

Lighting: To achieve varied brightness levels and simulate different environmental conditions, we simulate four distinct sun heights and nine solar azimuths. This approach allows us to analyze the impact of sun height on image brightness and select optimal values for rendering. We found that for the 4 desired heights of the sun, the maximum variation of brightness can be achieved using the values of 3°, 8°, 17° and 57° of the sun altitudes (Fig. 8). Similarly, we determined the values of the azimuth parameter to achieve a broad variation of brightness but also of color hues (Fig. 8). A prerequisite for using these parameters is the ability to adjust the sun's position. Since HDRI sky photos, which offer more realistic lighting and dynamic color distribution due to the presence of clouds, do not allow for control of the sun's position, we use a physical cloudless sky to maintain flexibility in sun placement.

Rendering: We employ a combined CPU and GPU rendering pipeline to efficiently generate images. This approach, known as "XPU rendering," distributes tasks using a procedural dependency graph, enabling optimal performance. By rendering multiple images in parallel using 1x AMD 5950X CPU and 2x RTX 3090 GPU, we achieve fast processing times, with each 331 px image taking approximately 1.8 seconds to render.

The outcome of this method is the creation of three synthetic datasets: UNIRI-SeaState-S1500 (labeled S1500), containing 12,000 images divided into 8 balanced classes, and two reduced versions, UNIRI-SeaState-S750 (labeled S750) and UNIRI-SeaState-S150 (labeled S150), with 750 and 150 images per class, respectively (Table III).

Fig. 7. Waves generator setup in Houdini. Right pane: procedural nodes used to compose a 3D scene with parameters shown in the rightmost panel. Middle pane: wireframe representation of waves' shape (blue) with simulated foam (yellow particles). Bottom-left pane: the dependency graph used for distributed foam simulation. Left pane: rendered preview in high resolution (662 px).

Fig. 8. Synthesized images with the maximum range of brightness and hue variations. Rows (top to bottom) show renders with the same sun altitude (3° , 8° , 17° and 57°). Sun azimuth changes by columns (left to right: 1° , 11° , 27° , 72° , 159° , 326° , 333° , 336° and 339°).

TABLE III. CLASS DISTRIBUTION IN THE UNIRI-SEASTATE SYNTHETIC DATASETS

UNIRI-SeaState synthset	Sea state (Bft)								Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
UNIRI-SeaState-S150 frames	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	1,200
UNIRI-SeaState-S750 frames	750	750	750	750	750	750	750	750	6,000
UNIRI-SeaState-S1500 frames	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	12,000

Both datasets provide a comprehensive range of sea states under various conditions, supporting the development of robust models for sea state estimation. A sample of generated images is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Samples of synthesized images rendered with different lighting conditions. Top row (left to right): classes Bft 1-4. Bottom row (left to right): classes Bft 5-8.

C. Synthetic Data Quality Assessment

Quantitative evaluation of the synthetic dataset was conducted using the FAISS metric [33], employing the clip-ViT-B-32 model with Flat L2 indexes [34]. This evaluation was integrated into the synthesis process to continuously monitor the domain gap between synthetic and real images, as well as between individual classes within both datasets. FAISS was selected due to its capability to identify the most and least similar images for each query, enabling iterative refinement of the synthetic dataset. A total of 150 images per class from both real and synthetic datasets—amounting to 2400 images—were compared. The diagonal white line in the similarity matrix represents the highest similarity score (FAISS score of 1.00), indicating a perfect match of each image with itself.

The uniformity observed in the synthetic dataset, as illustrated in Fig. 10, can be attributed to the controlled consistency of wave height ranges corresponding to each class, the linear variation of wave direction from 0 to 360 degrees, and the uniform sampling of illumination conditions. In contrast, the real dataset shown in Fig. 10 appears considerably more heterogeneous.

Within individual classes, regions of higher similarity may correspond to sequences of images extracted from the same video. For example, in class 8, two distinct groups of highly similar images can be identified (brighter areas), which are markedly different from each other (darker areas). Notably, some images within these groups exhibit greater similarity to images from class 5 than to their own class 8 counterparts. The use of FAISS allowed us to observe a rapid decrease in image similarity across all compared datasets.

Fig. 10. Visualization of FAISS analysis as a contrasted heatmap. The upper-left quadrant (green numbers) represents the real dataset, sorted by classes (from 1 to 8), and the lower-right quadrant represents the synthset (blue numbers).

Table IV presents the average FAISS similarity scores computed between images from various dataset partitions: training and validation subsets of the real dataset, the complete synthetic dataset compared to the training and validation subsets of the real dataset, and as a baseline, within the training subset of the real dataset.

For each pairing, the average similarity scores of the nearest, second nearest, and third nearest neighbors are aggregated. Excluding the perfect self-match (nearest similarity = 1.00) observed in the real/train versus real/train comparison, the highest subsequent similarity (second nearest) is 0.38 within the Bft 2 class, indicating a pronounced gap even among images of the same class in this dataset partition. Testing on the real/valid subset yields a maximum similarity of 0.35 (Bft 1). When applying the FAISS model trained on real/valid to the real/train data, the highest similarity score of 0.20 arises in the Bft 6 class, whereas Bft 5 images exhibit greater divergence, comparable to the distances between synthetic images (0.05–0.06). Synthetic images display generally low similarity scores relative to real/train and real/valid sets but maintain a narrow similarity range (0.03–0.05), reflecting the aforementioned controlled uniformity in their generation.

The FAISS analysis suggests that a substantial reduction of the domain gap between synthetic and real images is unlikely as long as significant variability persists within the real datasets themselves. This inherent variability can be attributed to the fractal nature of sea waves, characterized by self-similar and complex patterns across multiple scales.

Following the generation of synthetic datasets, we evaluated the quality of the synthesized images by examining their similarity to corresponding classes in the real dataset using the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [35]. FID quantifies the difference between the distributions of generated and real

images by comparing their mean and covariance statistics, using features extracted from images via the Inception convolutional neural network. Lower FID scores indicate greater similarity and higher sample diversity within the generated images.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE FAISS SIMILARITY SCORES BETWEEN IMAGES OF DIFFERENT DATASETS (TRAIN AND VALIDATION PORTIONS OF THE REAL DATASET AND THE ENTIRE SYNTHSET).

Training dataset		real /train			real /valid		
Testing dataset	Bft#	Nearest	2nd nearest	3rd nearest	Nearest	2nd nearest	3rd nearest
real/train	1	1.00	0.19	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
	2	1.00	0.38	0.37	0.12	0.11	0.11
	3	1.00	0.29	0.24	0.12	0.12	0.11
	4	1.00	0.25	0.25	0.19	0.18	0.16
	5	1.00	0.19	0.15	0.06	0.05	0.05
	6	1.00	0.25	0.21	0.20	0.19	0.18
	7	1.00	0.30	0.20	0.13	0.13	0.12
	8	1.00	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.13
	Σ	8.00	2.00	1.74	1.14	1.09	1.05
synth	1	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
	2	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03
	3	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05
	4	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
	5	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03
	6	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03
	7	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
	8	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03
	Σ	0.35	0.33	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.29

For reference, we compared FID scores between the training and test subsets of the real dataset (Table V) and between the synthetic dataset and the real training subset (Table VI).

TABLE V. FID SCORES BETWEEN TRAINING AND TESTING PARTS OF THE UNIRI-SEASTATE-R750 REAL DATASETS

		Test Set Class							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Training Set Class	1	102.65	151.77	170.68	244.2	197.46	188.66	230.75	262.07
	2	186.21	125.41	145.02	121.63	199.23	183.21	253.32	289.74
	3	191.17	133.02	89.08	93.2	151.6	135.88	220.82	238.8
	4	212.24	160.29	92.51	86.26	115.57	105.46	213.51	191.03
	5	207.18	170.28	98.5	107.64	94.82	89.79	187.94	161.52
	6	205.78	172.66	104.6	102.11	99.39	83.58	193.86	160.83
	7	221.24	202.65	142.87	160.14	112.45	125.07	181.92	166.16
	8	226.32	222.2	152.63	214.58	120.3	129.02	191.18	142.09

In Table V, which compares real images in training and test sets, the lowest FID scores appear along the diagonal, reflecting the highest similarity within the same classes. Values typically gradually increase farther from the diagonal, corresponding to greater differences in sea state.

Similar trends are observed in Table VI, which compares synthetic and real data, except for class 7, probably because only two source videos were available in the real training set so the distribution of samples is not uniform.

TABLE VI. FID SCORES BETWEEN UNIRI-SEAState-S1500 SYNTHETIC AND TRAINING PART OF THE UNIRI-SEAState-R750 REAL DATASETS

		Synthetic class							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Real class	1	208.21	213.17	239.15	253.73	244.75	299.65	235.73	318.24
	2	247.13	202.13	207.98	248.87	215.63	277.49	222.53	307.46
	3	314.84	247.11	165.85	262	170.79	241.35	190.74	265.31
	4	227.58	237.33	174.92	205.32	173.71	235.42	171.14	224.06
	5	227.5	258.21	176.69	225.89	169.33	213.18	155.4	181.31
	6	238.24	266.32	197.5	258.54	186.07	211.96	165.3	174.52
	7	290.4	322.48	280.42	307.16	277.13	298.75	207.35	233.86
	8	284.76	336.48	265.84	283.04	261.19	274.52	163.07	105.57

Overall, these results demonstrate a strong correspondence between synthesized images and their real-class counterparts, confirming the suitability of synthetic data for augmenting training sets.

IV. MODEL ARCHITECTURES

In this work, we evaluate the performance of several state-of-the-art model architectures that have shown promising results in handling complex visual patterns and domain adaptation. In addition to ResNet [36], a convolutional neural network architecture that showed best performance with sea state classification in [12], we consider Transformer based models and models that combine convolutional and attention mechanisms, namely CoAtNet [37], XciT [38], Swin Transformer [39] and DeiT III [40].

The used model architectures are described in brief in the following subsections.

A. Resnet

ResNet (Residual Network) [36] is a deep convolutional neural network architecture designed to address the vanishing gradient problem in very deep networks. ResNet introduced residual blocks, which include skip connections or shortcuts to facilitate the flow of gradients during training, which helps with the vanishing gradient problem and allows for the training of significantly deeper networks. ResNet has proven to be highly effective for various computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and segmentation. In this experiment, we use ResNet as a representative of traditional convolutional approach in the ResNet-101d variant as an improved version of the best performing network in previous study [12], ResNet-101 and a in a simpler Resnet18d configuration.

B. CoAtNet (Combining Convolutions and Transformers)

The CoAtNet architecture [37] seeks to merge the benefits of convolutional neural networks and transformer architectures. It combines the high model capacity and scalability of transformers with the fast convergence speed of CNNs. This is

achieved by integrating both convolutional layers and transformer blocks, leveraging the local feature extraction and translation equivariance of CNNs alongside the global context modeling of transformers.

The architecture consists of five stages, starting with an initial 2-layer convolutional stem followed by multiple convolutional MBConv blocks, and concluding with one or more transformer-like stages known as TFMrel. The convolutional stages reduce the spatial dimensions of the input, helping manage computational complexity, while the transformer stages apply global relative attention.

CoAtNet achieves state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance in low-data regimes due to the inductive biases of CNNs, yet it also excels with large datasets, benefiting from the scalability of transformer models [37].

In this experiment, we use the CoAtNet-0 and CoAtNet-1 variants of the architecture, differing only in number of blocks in intermediate stages between MBConv and TFMrel stage.

C. XCiT (Cross-Covariance Image Transformers)

The Cross-Covariance Image Transformers (XCiT) architecture [38] introduces a novel approach to processing image data, focusing on enhancing computational efficiency and scalability. Unlike traditional self-attention mechanisms, XCiT employs cross-covariance attention, which operates across channels rather than spatial tokens. This results in linear complexity with respect to sequence length, significantly reducing computational complexity and memory requirements compared to the quadratic complexity of standard self-attention.

Cross-covariance attention focuses on a fixed number of channels, regardless of the number of tokens, making XCiT more suitable for larger input images. To maintain spatial relationships between patches, XCiT incorporates local patch interaction modules. These modules consist of two depth-wise 3x3 convolutional layers with batch normalization and GELU non-linearity, complementing the global features captured by cross-covariance attention with fine-grained spatial details. Each XCiT module combines cross-covariance attention, local patch interaction, and a point-wise feed-forward network with a single hidden layer. The XCiT network stacks multiple XCiT modules, followed by global aggregation with class attention layers and therefore achieves accuracy of standard vision transformers while offering improved computational efficiency.

In this paper, we use the XCiT-S12 variant, which is a stacked configuration with 12 repeating XCiT stages, with embedding dimensionality of 384, 8 attention heads in the cross-covariance attention, and with 8x8 patch size.

D. Swin Transformer

The Swin Transformer architecture [39] aims to reduce computational complexity compared to traditional Transformer models by achieving linear complexity with image size. It constructs hierarchical feature maps by starting with small patches and merging them in deeper layers.

Swin Transformer computes self-attention locally within

non-overlapping windows, shifting these windows between layers to enhance modeling power while maintaining efficiency. This design allows cross-window connections, providing connections to windows of preceding layers and improving both computational efficiency and model performance.

The Swin Transformer processes images by first splitting them into 4x4 non-overlapping patches, projecting these as tokens into a higher dimension using a linear embedding layer, and then applying multiple Swin Transformer blocks. Each block includes a shifted window-based multi-head self-attention module followed by a 2-layer MLP with GELU non-linearity.

The network consists of four stages: an initial stage with linear embedding, followed by three stages of patch merging and Swin Transformer blocks. This hierarchical structure produces feature representations similar to those of convolutional neural networks. The architecture has proven successful in various computer vision tasks, including object detection and classification.

In this experiment, we use the base Swin-B model, and the smaller “tiny” variant Swin-T with the window size set to $M = 7$. The query dimension of each head is $d = 32$, and the expansion layer of each MLP is $\alpha = 4$, for all experiments.

E. DeiT III

DEIT III (Data-efficient image Transformers III) [40] focuses on optimizing the training process of the Vision Transformer (ViT) [41] model, especially in scenarios with limited data, without altering its underlying structure. The Transformer architecture consists of feedforward neural networks and self-attention mechanisms that enable the model to capture global dependencies within the input sequence.

The ViT model applies the Transformer architecture, originally designed for natural language processing, to image data by converting 2D images into 1D sequences of patch embeddings. This process involves dividing images into 4 non-overlapping patches, projecting them into high-dimensional vectors, and adding positional information to encode spatial layout.

In our experiment, we utilized the ViT-Base architecture, featuring 12 layers, 12 heads, and a 16x16 patch size with 768-dimensional embeddings.

DeiT III enhances ViT by achieving competitive performance with significantly less training data [40]. This is accomplished through advanced regularization techniques (e.g., stochastic depth, repeated augmentation) and optimization strategies (e.g., AdamW with a cosine learning rate schedule, label smoothing). These improvements make DeiT III well-suited for fine-tuning on smaller datasets such as ours.

V. EXPERIMENT SETUP

A. Choice of model architecture

The chosen computer vision model architectures described above were first evaluated to select the best performing model for further experiments and to determine their effectiveness for

sea state estimation task. Each model architecture was first fine-tuned starting from weights pretrained on ImageNet-21k or Imagenet-1k [42], depending on availability. Fine-tuning was done using our UNIRI-SeaState-R150 dataset of 150 real images per class for 20 epochs, and evaluated on the test set. The batch size for all models was 8. The AdamW optimizer with label smoothing cross entropy loss was used for training the models, with an initial learning rate of $5e-4$, 10 patience epochs, cosine scheduler, and decay rate of 0.1.

A summary of model sizes, parameters, and initial pretrained weights used as the starting point is shown in Table VII. All models are retrieved from <https://huggingface.co/timm/<Pretrained model weights>>.

TABLE VII. SUMMARY OF SELECTED MODEL ARCHITECTURES

Network Architecture	Total params	Image size	Pretrained model weights
Resnet-18d	11.7M	224	resnet18d.ra2_in1k
ResNet-101d	42.7 M	224	resnet101d.ra2_in1k
CoAtNet-0	25M	224	coatnet_0_rw_224.sw_in1k
CoAtNet-1	42M	224	coatnet_1_rw_224.sw_in1k
XCiT-small	26M	224	xcit_small_12_p8_224.fb_in1k
Swin-T	29M	224	swin_tiny_patch4_window7_224.ms_in22k
Swin-B	88M	224	swin_base_patch4_window7_224.ms_in22k
Swin-B	88M	384	swin_base_patch4_window12_384_in22k
DEIT-III base	87M	224	deit3_base_patch16_224.fb_in22k_ft_in1k
DEIT-III base	87M	384	deit3_base_patch16_384.fb_in22k_ft_in1k

For models with the 224x224 pixels input image size, the images in the training dataset were center-cropped, while for the models with 384x384 input size, the images were rescaled from the original 331x331 size in the dataset.

During the training process, we employed RandAugment data augmentation [43] for all models. RandAugment randomly applies a variety of augmentations, including geometric transformations, color adjustments, noise addition, and partial image masking. Although the DEIT-III paper [40] recommends the simplified ThreeAugment method, which includes grayscale conversion, solarization, color jitter, and Gaussian blur, preliminary tests showed that RandAugment performed better. Therefore, we consistently used RandAugment across all models in our subsequent experiments.

In total 10 models were trained, one of each architecture. The models were evaluated on the test set according to the classification and regression metrics described below, and the best performing model selected for further experiments.

B. Model optimization

After selecting the best-performing architecture, we experimented with different dataset configurations to be used for models fine-tuning by increasing the number of real images and mixing real and synthesized images in different ratios. As in the previous experiment, the model was fine-tuned from Imagenet-21 pretrained weights for 20 epochs.

Also, since intuitively the color information seems to carry little information relevant for sea state classification, but color can vary dramatically depending on the time of day, angle to

the sun, weather, etc. and can be difficult to capture all variations for different classes, we repeated the experiment with desaturated, grayscale versions of the datasets (both for training and testing).

Finally, we explore various voting schemes for combining predictions from multiple frames on the best-performing model.

C. Evaluation Metrics

In evaluating our sea state estimation models, we utilized standard metrics commonly accepted in the field: precision, recall, and F1 score. These metrics were calculated for each individual class to assess the models' ability to accurately identify distinct sea states.

Precision, also known as the Positive Predictive Value (PPV), is the proportion of true positive cases among all cases predicted as positive. It is a measure of a model's accuracy in identifying cases as belonging to a particular class. A higher precision indicates a lower rate of false positives. The formula for precision is given as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

where TP represents the number of true positives, and FP denotes the number of false positives.

Recall (also known as sensitivity or True Positive Rate, TPR) assesses the model's ability to correctly identify all actual instances of a given class. It is particularly critical in scenarios where failing to detect a condition could have serious implications, and it addresses the question: Of all the actual sea states of a class, how many were identified?

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

where FN is the number of false negatives.

Both precision and recall are balanced by the F1 score, which is the harmonic mean of the two. It is particularly useful when both false positives and false negatives have similar consequences, as it provides a clear measure of the trade-off between precision (Positive Predictive Value) and recall (True Positive Rate). Moreover, the F1 Score is valuable in the presence of imbalanced class distributions, where the cost of misclassification can differ across classes, offering a comprehensive view of a model's performance. The F1 Score is calculated using the formula:

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times PPV \times TPR}{PPV + TPR} \quad (3)$$

In this formula, PPV is the number of true positive results divided by the number of all positive results predicted by the classifier, and TPR is the number of true positive results divided by the number of all actual positives. The F1 score effectively captures both the precision and robustness of the classifier's positive predictions.

For an overarching assessment of the model performance

across all classes, we utilize Accuracy, which gives us the ratio of correctly predicted observations to the total observations.

We also consider Within 1-class accuracy, which considers a prediction to be true if it is exactly right or off by just one class. In sea state classification, the visual differences between adjacent Beaufort numbers can be subtle (e.g., the difference between 3 and 4 Bft is less dramatic than between 2 and 6 Bft), and even human experts might disagree on borderline cases. In practical applications, being off by one class usually has minor operational consequences compared to larger errors.

Individual metrics are complemented by the Macro Average, which calculates metrics for each class independently and then takes the average, treating all classes equally.

$$Macro\ Average = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{class=1}^n \text{metric rate for each class.} \quad (4)$$

This means it does not take label imbalance into account. Conversely, the Weighted Average takes the label imbalance into account and calculates metrics for each class proportionally to its presence in the dataset.

$$WA = \frac{\sum_{class=1}^n \text{metric rate} \times \text{number of instances per class}}{\text{total number of instances}}. \quad (5)$$

Mean absolute error (MAE) is the arithmetic average of absolute errors, or absolute differences between the true values x_i and the predicted values y_i .

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |e_i|}{n}. \quad (6)$$

Root mean square error (RMSE) is a similar measure to the MAE, but it is more sensitive to large errors:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}. \quad (7)$$

Maximum error is the largest absolute difference between predicted and actual values, and it provides insight into the worst-case performance.

Bias is calculated as empirical bias of the model calculated on the dataset as the mean error. It measures the average difference between predictions and actual values, revealing if a model systematically predicts values that are too high or too low.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evaluation results for models trained on the UNIRI-SeaState-R150 dataset, comprising 150 real sea state images per class are present in Table VIII. The `deit_base_patch16_LS` model with 384×384 input image size achieved the highest scores for most metrics, except for bias and maximum error. Notably, its maximum error of 5, while greater than most models except `xcit_small_12_p8_224`, was restricted to a few instances. Consequently, further experiments focused on the `deit_base_patch16_LS` architecture (referred to DEiT III in the following text). All models exhibited positive bias, indicating a

tendency to overestimate sea states. This could reflect differences in recording conditions between the training and test sets, or more globally overestimated values in the training data compared to the test set obtained on a different ship.

The DEiT III model was subsequently fine-tuned on multiple variants of the UNIRI-SeaState datasets, encompassing real images (R150, R750), synthetic images (S150, S750, S1500), and combined real and synthetic sets (R150+S150, R750+S750, R750+S1500). Training employed both original RGB images and grayscale-converted versions, with evaluation performed on a consistent test set—apart from grayscale conversion for grayscale-trained models. Table IX details these outcomes.

Fine-tuning the DEiT III model on the combined real and synthetic data, R750+S1500 (Grayscale) dataset delivered the best overall results, with top Within-1 Accuracy (89%), macro average F1 score (53%), lowest Mean Absolute Error (0.619), and minimum RMSE (0.9276). The model also achieved the second-best accuracy of 50%. The highest accuracy of 51% was achieved by the model that was also trained on the combined dataset, but with half the synthetic data (R750+S750). It also achieved the second highest macro average F1 score of 52% and the second lowest bias.

Models fine-tuned on real images (R150, R750) generally surpassed those trained exclusively on synthetic images (S150, S750, S1500). Synthetic models, however, exhibited higher Within-1 Accuracy but lower overall Accuracy.

The results show that the combination of real and synthetic data for model fine-tuning contributed the most to the improvement of model performance, however, the small difference in model performance achieved with a twofold increase in synthetic data suggests that there is a plateau when increasing synthetic data no longer affects the improvement of model performance.

One of the primary limitations of synthetic data in computer vision tasks is its inherent inability to fully replicate the complexity of natural phenomena and their underlying cause-and-effect dynamics, thereby limiting the achievement of maximal visual realism. In our approach, the sea surface is simulated as a continuous 3D dynamic surface with peaks and valleys, textured by foam patterns whose distribution depends on particle emissions from wave crests taking into account environmental factors such as sun position and time of day that affect the color distribution.

TABLE VIII. CLASSIFICATION AND REGRESSION METRICS FOR MODELS FINETUNED ON REAL IMAGES (R150 DATASET). THE BEST RESULTS ARE MARKED IN BOLD.

Model	Image size	Accuracy	Within 1 class	Macro	MAE	Bias	RMSE	Max
			accuracy	Avg F1				error
ResNet-18d	224	40%	78%	44%	0,899	0,261	1,291	4
ResNet-101d	224	37%	74%	40%	0,954	0,143	1,315	5
coatnet_0_rw_224	224	43%	78%	42%	0,854	0,394	1,253	4
coatnet_1_rw_224	224	43%	78%	42%	0,842	0,430	1,223	4
deit_base_patch16_LS	224	44%	80%	43%	0,814	0,256	1,202	4
deit_base_patch16_LS	384	46%	82%	49%	0,772	0,152	1,162	5
swin_tiny_patch4_window7_224	224	41%	78%	44%	0,874	0,236	1,260	4
swin_base_patch4_window7_224	224	42%	79%	39%	0,837	0,432	1,206	4
swin_base_patch4_window12_384	384	42%	79%	37%	0,844	0,321	1,225	4
xcit_small_12_p8_224	224	45%	81%	42%	0,822	0,190	1,571	4

TABLE IX. RESULTS FOR DEiT III MODELS TRAINED ON DIFFERENT DATASETS WITH INPUT IMAGE SIZE 384. THE BEST RESULTS ARE MARKED IN BOLD, AND THE SECOND BEST IN ITALICS.

Training Set		Accuracy	Within-1 Accuracy	Macro Avg F1	MAE	Bias	RMSE	Max error	F1 score per class							
									1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
R150	RGB	46%	82%	49%	0,772	0,152	1,1620	5	73%	68%	48%	36%	40%	33%	36%	57%
R750	RGB	40%	76%	38%	0,886	0,216	1,2414	5	80%	67%	44%	41%	23%	27%	22%	0%
R150	Grayscale	42%	79%	47%	0,806	-0,155	1,1495	7	85%	68%	36%	34%	29%	34%	44%	49%
R750	Grayscale	44%	82%	47%	0,763	0,080	1,1067	7	79%	52%	48%	40%	26%	32%	46%	55%
S150	RGB	42%	87%	44%	0,726	-0,263	1,0487	7	77%	67%	30%	45%	20%	40%	10%	61%
S750	RGB	35%	80%	38%	0,874	-0,545	1,165	3	84%	54%	12%	4%	17%	47%	31%	54%
S1500	RGB	35%	80%	40%	0,882	-0,706	1,1810	3	82%	51%	31%	10%	15%	42%	34%	59%
S150	Grayscale	38%	84%	40%	0,792	-0,526	1,0788	3	59%	66%	28%	35%	20%	39%	16%	60%
S750	Grayscale	35%	75%	38%	0,929	-0,701	1,246	3	86%	60%	19%	2%	10%	43%	29%	54%
S1500	Grayscale	36%	77%	42%	0,895	-0,675	1,2106	3	84%	63%	44%	0%	19%	34%	28%	62%
R150+S150	RGB	49%	85%	49%	0,694	0,197	1,0659	3	89%	76%	53%	42%	40%	19%	26%	49%
R750+S750	RGB	51%	83%	52%	0,716	0,029	1,127	3	93%	81%	51%	46%	35%	20%	39%	52%
R750+S1500	RGB	42%	77%	38%	0,873	0,411	1,2680	4	80%	70%	42%	44%	36%	18%	1%	14%
R150+S150	Grayscale	47%	84%	47%	0,745	0,307	1,1441	6	79%	73%	52%	41%	40%	22%	52%	15%
R750+S750	Grayscale	50%	80%	50%	0,727	0,090	1,113	3	83%	78%	56%	44%	41%	22%	25%	51%
R750+S1500	Grayscale	50%	89%	53%	0,619	-0,014	0,9276	3	83%	73%	53%	43%	31%	29%	47%	67%

However, in order to balance realism with computational feasibility, fine-grained effects such as individual water droplets and wind-driven spray layers, particularly pronounced at higher Beaufort states, are not modeled. This gap in realism, known as the "reality gap," can lead to degraded performance of models trained exclusively on synthetic data when tested on real-world datasets.

Also, synthetic data primarily serves to supplement real datasets by enriching variability and addressing data scarcity, especially for rare or underrepresented sea and weather states or environmental features that are not frequently encountered or recorded in operational sampling. For example, our synthetic dataset includes 1440 variations (180 for each Beaufort scale state), which is 12 times more than in the real data we have and contributed to improving the accuracy of wave classification in all tested hybrid dataset configurations with different ratios of real to synthetic data between 2 and 6%.

While most models achieved higher accuracy for lower sea state classes (0, 1), their performance declined for higher classes (5, 6, 7) for which we had fewer real samples. However, although the generator has no limitations in modeling dynamic 3D surfaces and modeling different conditions that can be used to model sea states, the limited number of real samples restricted both the ability to generate credible synthetic data and to test the consistency of synthetic and real domains in open sea conditions (e.g. Beaufort 7 or 8 and above) and consequently limited the evaluation of model performance for these classes in real conditions.

Notably, DEiT III model fine-tuned on R750+S1500 (Grayscale) demonstrated balanced accuracy across all classes. Models fine-tuned on synthetic data (S150, S750, S1500) showed negative bias (tendency to underestimate), and models fine-tuned on real data (R150, R750) exhibited positive bias. Models fine-tuned on the combined dataset, R750+S1500 (Grayscale), achieved nearly neutral bias (-0.014), suggesting balanced predictions.

The hybrid approach has been shown to exploit the complementary strengths of both data types and achieve better performance by exploiting the synergistic effect of combining

imperfect real data with domain-shifted synthetic data. The synthetic data provides a dense, continuous distribution of samples across the class spectrum. By adding these samples to the training set, the synthetic data acts as a regularizer. It forces the model to learn features that are consistent across variations (e.g., wave geometry, texture and structural characteristics) rather than overfitting to not discriminant variables in the real dataset (e.g., a specific position of the sun, or color). While synthetic data provides diversity, it suffers from a domain gap. However, when mixed with real data, the real samples act as "semantic anchors." They constrain the optimization process, ensuring that the decision boundaries shaped by the abundant synthetic data remain aligned with the target real-world domain.

For performance comparison Fig. 11 presents the confusion matrices for the DEiT III model trained on R750 (grayscale) real data as a baseline for grayscale models and the best-performing DEiT III model trained on both real and synthetic data, a R750+S1500 grayscale set.

Model trained on the R750+S1500 set demonstrates a 6% increase in accuracy compared to the model trained on the R750 set. Moreover, model trained on the R750+S1500 set substantially reduces misclassifications in Classes 2, 3, 5, and 8. In contrast, the model trained on R750 set more frequently underestimates the sea state, as evidenced by a higher concentration of misclassifications below the diagonal. The model trained on the R750+S1500 exhibits a more balanced distribution of misclassifications around the diagonal, reflecting improved differentiation between adjacent sea states.

The obtained results show both the need for integrating synthetic and real data and the importance of their proper ratio in the training set that will ensure effective data augmentation and sampling of sparse data, as well as domain shift in the function of increasing accuracy and generalization of the model.

Examples of correct classifications of the best performing DEiT III model that was fine-tuned on R750+S1500 datasets are shown in Table X, and examples of incorrect classifications are shown in Table XI.

Fig. 11. Confusion matrices of DEiT III models finetuned for 20 epochs from Imagenet-21k pretrained model on (a) R750 dataset (real images only), (b) R750+S1500 dataset (both real and synthetic images). All images were previously converted to grayscale.

TABLE X. EXAMPLES OF CORRECT SEA STATE ESTIMATIONS FOR DEIT III MODEL FINETUNED ON R750+S1500 DATASET.

Input image				
Ground truth	1	2	3	4
Prediction	1	2	3	4
Input Image				
Ground truth	5	6	7	8
Prediction	5	6	7	8

TABLE XII. EXAMPLES OF INCORRECT SEA STATE ESTIMATIONS FOR DEIT III MODEL FINETUNED ON R750+S1500 DATASET.

Ground Truth	1	2	3	4
Prediction	2	3	2	3
Input Image				
Ground truth	5	6	7	8
Prediction	6	8	8	6

A. Temporal voting framework

To mitigate individual frame misclassifications and exploit the temporal consistency of sea states, we implemented a temporal voting framework that aggregates predictions across video frames in video sequences. Since the sea state remains constant within a temporal window in a single video recording, multiple frames from the same sequence can be aggregated to

mitigate transient errors and ensuring a more stable, robust classification.

For each video sequence, we extracted n frames sampled at 6 FPS, and obtained individual classifications. Two aggregation strategies were evaluated: taking the arithmetic mean of the frame-level classifications, and selecting the modal (most frequent) class. The assumption is that while individual frames

may be misclassified due to factors such as temporary wave configurations or image quality issues, the dominant pattern across multiple frames should better represent the true sea state. The temporal aggregation serves as a natural noise reduction mechanism, potentially eliminating outlier classifications that could occur in single-frame analysis.

For the mean-based approach, regression metrics such as MAE and RMSE were computed using the raw real-valued means, while classification metrics like accuracy were calculated after rounding the means to the nearest integer to conform with the discrete Beaufort scale classes.

Fig. 12 shows the root mean square error for DEiT III model fine-tuned on R750+S1500 on grayscale images for different numbers of frames (without voting) and when temporal time frame voting is applied. It is clear that both mean and mode voting schemes increasingly improve the error with an increased number of frames, up to about 20 frames, after which there is no significant improvement.

Both approaches significantly improve the classification results, with increase of accuracy of about 7% and a decrease of maximum error by 1 Bft. For most measures, aggregating the results of 20 frames by the most common prediction (mode) gives better results than aggregating by the mean value (Table XII).

However, the measures sensitive to large errors, the within 1-

class accuracy and the RMSE, are improved by using the mean approach, with the highest value of 96.32% and 0.7348, respectively, for the 20-frame voting scheme. Considering that in this task it is important to achieve the smallest possible error, voting schemes with aggregation according to the mean of the predictions are the most suitable in this case.

Fig. 12. RMSE for DEiT III model finetuned on R750+S1500 dataset, using frame-by-frame prediction or voting by taking the mode of predictions for n frames.

TABLE XII. SEA STATE ESTIMATION RESULTS OF DEiT III MODEL WITH AND WITHOUT TEMPORAL VOTING FRAMEWORK

Voting scheme	Accuracy	Within 1-class Accuracy	Macro Avg F1	MAE	Bias	RMSE	Max error
Frame by frame (no voting)	49.79%	88.78%	53.37%	0.6186	-0.014	0.9276	3
Mean of 20 frames	55.15%	96.32%	57.99%	0.5423	-0.001	0.7348	2.05
Mode of 20 frames	57.35%	90.44%	58.06%	0.5221	-0.002	0.8445	2
Mean of 25 frames	56.90%	95.69%	61.91%	0.5510	-0.001	0.7365	2
Mode of 25 frames	56.03%	91.38%	59.59%	0.5259	-0.002	0.8356	2

Fig. 13. Confusion matrices of DEiT III models finetuned on R750+S1500 (a) with voting using the most common prediction of 20 consecutive frames (mode) (b) with voting using mean of 25 consecutive frames.

With respect to both accuracy and F1-score, the voting schemes yield comparable performance, with a maximum difference of approximately 2% between the best- and worst-performing configurations. Specifically, 20-frame Mode voting scheme achieves the highest overall accuracy of 57.35%, while the 20-frame Mean scheme yields the lowest at 55.15%. In contrast, the highest overall F1-score of 61.91% is obtained by the 25-frame Mean voting scheme, whereas the lowest of 57.99% by the 20-frame Mean voting scheme.

To compare class-wise performance, confusion matrices for the 20-frame Mode voting scheme and the 25-frame Mean voting scheme are presented in Fig. 13.

The voting scheme has significantly improved overall accuracy and reduced misclassifications. There are fewer off-diagonal elements, especially for distant classes. The model now performs exceptionally well on the lowest and highest severity classes. The middle severity range (Classes 4-6) still presents challenges, but misclassifications are mostly limited to adjacent classes

B. Discussion

Our previous research [12], demonstrated the feasibility of using convolutional neural networks such as ResNet-101 for sea state estimation, achieving high accuracy rates under controlled conditions. However, like many computer vision systems, the models showed limitations when encountering conditions that differed significantly from the training data. This phenomenon, known as domain shift, presents a particular challenge in maritime applications where lighting conditions, weather patterns, and wave characteristics can vary dramatically across different locations and seasons.

To address these limitations, we made several key modifications in this experiment. First, we defined a new pipeline for generating synthetic data of diverse sea states across a wide range of weather and atmospheric conditions and geographical influences, thereby expanding our existing training dataset with artificially generated sea state images. Second, for sea state estimation, we selected state-of-the-art classification methods that have shown promising results in handling complex visual patterns, capturing long-term dependencies, and adapting to different visual conditions and domain changes. Specifically, we fine-tuned and compared the performance of CoAtNet, which combines convolution and self-attention mechanisms, XCiT's cross-covariance attention approach, Swin Transformer's hierarchical feature learning, and DeiT III's distillation-based training strategy. All these architectures showed improvement and better adaptation of the domain shift compared to the traditional deep convolutional network ResNet-101 and achieved significantly higher precision, from 4% more for the Swin Transformer to 9% more for the DeiT III network.

The best results for our sea state prediction task were shown by the DeiT III model, which achieved an accuracy of 46%, within 1-class accuracy of 82%, and an F1 score of 49% and with MAE of 0.77 and RMSE of 1,162. We further tested this architecture on different dataset configurations by increasing the number of training samples and combining different ratios

of synthetic and real images, with color images and grayscale versions of those images.

The most accurate and balanced results overall were shown to be achieved by the DeiT III model fine-tuned on the combined R750+S1500 dataset (in grayscale). Significant improvements were achieved, namely an accuracy of 46%, within 1-class accuracy of 82% and an F1 of 54%, which is an increase compared to the DeiT III model trained only on real images on set R150, of 4% for accuracy and F1 score, and 7% for within 1-class accuracy. The model also shows generally better performance and significant improvements in distinguishing adjacent sea states and makes significantly fewer errors in estimating sea state. The severity of classification errors can be quantified by the regression metrics MAE and maximum errors. For example, a model may achieve similar classification accuracy to others but show a significantly lower maximum error, indicating more reliable performance. In case of DeiT III model fine-tuned on R750+S1500 dataset (in grayscale) maximum class estimation error has dropped to 3 from 5 in the version trained on R150, with an average error below one class, its MAE was 0.61 while after fine-tuning on R150 it was 0.77, also the RMSE was 1.162 and dropped to 0.927. However, there's still room for improvement, particularly in the middle sea state range.

The idea of determining the sea state based on voting concerning the classification of about 20 successive frames has proven to be promising and much more reliable for assessing the sea state, regardless of whether the mean or mode strategy is used. The achieved results are an accuracy of 57%, within-1-class accuracy of 96%, and F1 of 61.91%, which is a significant increase compared to the DeiT III model fine-tuned on R150, namely 11% for accuracy, 14% for within-1-class accuracy and almost 13% for F1. The improvements are also reflected in the complementary regression metrics and show that the model has increased its accuracy by reducing the maximum error to only 2 classes from the initial 5 and that the mean average error is 0.55, or RMSE 0.7365, which is also a significant decrease.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research explores the application of computer vision methods to the automated real-time classification of sea states, contributing to the field of maritime safety and vessel energy efficiency. Building upon our previous research we greatly expanded our test set to explore the model robustness in challenging and varying weather conditions and explored state-of-the-art classification methods, including CoAtNet, XCiT, Swin Transformer, and DeiT III. Advanced image classification models, fine-tuned on our dataset, have effectively classified sea states within the operational envelope based on the Beaufort scale. Among these architectures, the DeiT III model emerged as the most effective, achieving an accuracy of 46%, a within-1-class accuracy of 82%, and an F1 score of 49%.

To enhance the variety of difficult-to-collect sea states, we introduced a novel pipeline for generating synthetic data, encompassing diverse sea states and atmospheric conditions. This augmented dataset significantly enhanced the robustness of our models.

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